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Economic Factors Influencing Teacher Shortage in Early Childhood Education in Ibadan South-West Nigeria

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Citation

Olawale, O. S., Adigun, A. S., Wumi, A. M., & Ayobami, S. N. (2024). Economic factors influencing teacher shortage in early childhood education in Ibadan South-West Nigeria. *Journal of International Accounting and Financial Management*, 1(1), 13-27.

Submitted: 28-Aug, 2024

Accepted: 27-Sep, 2024

Published: 29-Oct, 2025

Vol. 1, No. 1, 2024.

 10.62762/JIAFM.2024.000000

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Abstract

This study examined the economic factors influencing teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) in Ibadan South West, Nigeria. five specific purposes, five research questions and Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model developed by Bakker, Demerouti, de Boer, and Schaufeli (2003) as the theoretical framework guided this study.

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, a sample of approximately 200 teachers (100 from public schools and 100 from private schools) was selected using a stratified random sampling method. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to measure the key variables related to each research question. To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in early childhood education and educational research to confirm that it effectively measured the constructs of interest. A pilot study was conducted with a small subset of teachers (approximately 20) to refine the questionnaire items based on feedback. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument, with an acceptable threshold set at 0.7.

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings indicated that low salaries and high living costs significantly contribute to teacher attrition, with many educators seeking alternative employment to meet their financial needs. The study also revealed that public and private ECE teachers face distinct economic challenges, leading to variations in retention rates. Additionally, inadequate professional development and financial support were found to deter both existing and potential teachers from pursuing a career in ECE. Job insecurity further exacerbated the problem, particularly among private ECE

educators.

Based on the findings, several recommendations were made, including increasing salaries, implementing financial incentives, enhancing professional development opportunities, addressing job insecurity, providing housing support, increasing education funding, promoting ECE as a career, establishing mentorship programs, facilitating community involvement, and conducting regular assessments of teacher needs. By addressing these economic factors, stakeholders can improve teacher retention and ultimately enhance the quality of early childhood education in Ibadan South West.

Keywords: Early Childhood Education (ECE), Teacher Shortage, Economic Factors, Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, Teacher Retention, Public and Private Schools, Professional Development, Job Insecurity, Teacher Attrition

Introduction

The teaching profession is fundamentally a service-oriented vocation that plays a pivotal role in training individuals across various fields, contributing significantly to the growth and development of nations. Countries rely heavily on educators at all levels of the education system to facilitate societal progress. Despite the crucial role teachers play in shaping the future, many struggle to make ends meet due to meager salaries. In Nigeria, the current economic realities have compelled numerous teachers to leave their jobs for trading and other ventures, exacerbating the existing teacher shortage.

Teacher shortage is defined as the insufficient number of qualified educators to meet the educational demands of students in a particular region. This phenomenon occurs when there is an inadequate supply of teachers to fill available teaching positions (Boe, 2014). According to Thomas, DiNapoli, Garcia, Kini, Patrick, and Saunders (2024), teacher shortages reflect schools' inability to find qualified personnel to fill classroom vacancies. UNESCO (2024) notes that teacher shortages are a widespread issue, affecting not only developing countries but also many regions in Europe and North America. Vargas (2022) highlights that developed nations such as Australia, China, France, and the United States are also grappling with this challenge. Alarmingly, UNESCO (2024) reported that global attrition rates among primary teachers have nearly doubled, increasing from 4.62% in 2015 to 9.06% in 2022, with many educators leaving the profession within their first five years. Bryner (2021) indicated that turnover rates are rising, particularly within early childhood education.

Early Childhood Education (ECE) encompasses educational programs designed for children before they enter primary school, focusing on their cognitive, social, and emotional development from birth to age eight (Houten, 2009). Bryner (2021) pointed out that teacher shortages in early childhood education are a global issue, with significant shortages reported in countries like the United States and Germany, adversely affecting education quality (Bryner, 2021; Seeliger & Lindqvist, 2023). The Early Care and Education Consortium (2022) reported an unprecedented decline in the workforce, with two-thirds of early childhood centers facing staff shortages, primarily

driven by economic factors.

Economic factors encompass elements that affect the financial viability of an industry or society, including resource availability, government policies, inflation, and overall regional economic conditions. These factors exert both direct and indirect influences on social sectors, such as education (Ingersoll & Perda, 2009). Flores and Craig (2023) identified low pay as a critical economic factor contributing to early childhood teacher shortages. In Nigeria, the low salaries for early childhood educators make it challenging to meet personal and familial needs, resulting in a decline in the number of teachers and those pursuing teaching careers. Ingersoll, May, and Collins (2019) also identified low pay as a significant reason for teacher shortages in the United States, a situation mirrored in Nigeria, where inadequate compensation diminishes the profession's appeal.

Moreover, the lack of financial incentives for teachers to pursue further education and professional development exacerbates the shortage of qualified educators. Sutapa and Utari (2017) argued that the absence of incentives, such as bonuses and promotions, contributes to the teacher shortage issue. Edwards and Cheok (2018) emphasized that the high cost of living in urban areas makes it increasingly difficult for teachers to afford housing and basic necessities. In Nigeria, the elevated cost of living further complicates teachers' financial stability, exacerbating retention issues. The absence of housing subsidies and other financial support mechanisms can deter qualified individuals from remaining in the profession.

The challenge of inadequate funding is another significant obstacle to addressing teacher shortages in early childhood education. Cobbold (2015) highlighted that insufficient funding hampers efforts to attract and retain qualified teachers in Ghana, a sentiment echoed in Nigeria. Without adequate resources, training and development opportunities for teachers are compromised, leading to a shortage of qualified personnel in the ECE sector.

Among private early childhood educators, job insecurity presents an economic challenge. Mlangeni et al. (2015) noted that teachers in Malawi experience job insecurity due to the absence of permanent positions. This insecurity may deter qualified individuals from entering the ECE field, exacerbating teacher shortages. McGrath et al. (2020) further highlighted how the lack of job security contributes to the underrepresentation of male teachers in various regions.

Lamboy (2023) posited that limited resources allocated to the education system hinder in-service training for current teachers, impeding their professional development and ultimately affecting the quality of early childhood education. Additionally, inadequate funding for teacher training programs remains a pressing concern (Pipho, 1998). These programs are essential for equipping educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their roles; however, insufficient funding undermines their effectiveness, leading to a scarcity of qualified teachers in the ECE sector.

The high cost of education for aspiring teachers is another barrier to entry into the profession. Reinsfield and Lee (2021) noted that exorbitant fees deter individuals from low-income backgrounds from pursuing teaching careers, further exacerbating the

teacher shortage problem. Shein (2019) also highlighted that the financial burden associated with teacher training dissuades potential candidates from entering the field. Similar concerns were raised by Glackin and Adams (2016) regarding Indiana's teacher shortages, and Urwick and Kisa (2014) emphasized the high cost of teacher education as a contributing factor to teacher shortages in Uganda.

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, developed by Bakker, Demerouti, de Boer, and Schaufeli (2003), provides a theoretical framework for understanding the dynamics of workplace stress and satisfaction. The model posits that job demands—elements requiring sustained effort—can lead to stress and burnout, particularly when insufficient resources are available to mitigate these demands. Conversely, job resources—supportive elements such as positive leadership, career development opportunities, and a conducive work environment—can enhance motivation, job satisfaction, and ultimately, reduce turnover.

In the context of early childhood education in Ibadan, South West Nigeria, the JD-R model is instrumental in analyzing the economic factors contributing to teacher shortages. Job demands such as low salaries, lack of benefits, and job insecurity elevate stress and dissatisfaction among educators, increasing the likelihood of turnover. Research indicates that financial stress linked to inadequate salaries and benefits exacerbates job demands, leading to higher turnover rates.

However, sufficient job resources can mitigate the negative effects of these demands. Supportive leadership, professional development opportunities, and favorable working conditions are vital in enhancing teacher job satisfaction. Access to adequate facilities, classroom resources, and mentoring programs can improve retention rates. Mills et al. (2001) demonstrated that mentoring programs effectively reduce turnover and enhance job satisfaction. By ensuring that adequate job resources are available, administrators and policymakers can create a more supportive work environment, improving teacher retention and addressing the ongoing teacher shortage in Ibadan South West Local Government.

Statement of the Problem

Teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) pose significant challenges worldwide, affecting not only educational quality but also child development outcomes. The global nature of teacher shortages, as documented in countries like the United States, Germany, and Australia, highlights that this issue transcends economic development levels. In both developing and developed countries, ECE teacher shortages are driven largely by economic factors such as low pay, lack of benefits, job insecurity, and high living costs. Despite these trends, Nigeria faces unique economic constraints that exacerbate ECE teacher shortages, especially in local areas like Ibadan South West, where educators experience high financial stress in conjunction with limited support and professional development opportunities.

In Nigeria, economic challenges such as inadequate salaries, poor working conditions, and job insecurity have contributed to a sustained shortage of teachers, particularly in the ECE sector. Research has shown that low salaries in ECE can lead to teacher

dissatisfaction, high turnover rates, and a decreased interest in teaching careers. Moreover, the limited availability of financial incentives and the lack of professional development options further disincentivize teachers from continuing in or entering the profession. This economic reality forces many teachers to seek alternative employment, thereby compounding the issue of teacher shortages in ECE. Studies also suggest that high costs associated with professional training discourage new entrants into the field, making it challenging to replenish the teaching workforce. However, these studies are often broad, providing limited insight into the specific economic challenges faced by ECE teachers in Nigeria.

The existing literature has identified key economic factors impacting teacher shortages in other countries, such as insufficient pay, high cost of living, job insecurity, and lack of financial support for professional development. However, gaps remain in understanding how these factors affect ECE teacher shortages in Nigeria, particularly in Ibadan South West. For instance, while studies like those by Flores and Craig highlight low pay as a primary cause of teacher shortages, few have explored how local costs of living in Ibadan influence ECE teacher retention. Additionally, current research lacks insights into the unique financial challenges faced by private-sector ECE teachers, who may experience even greater job insecurity and limited access to benefits than their public-sector counterparts.

This study aims to fill these gaps by examining the specific economic factors that influence teacher shortages in early childhood education within Ibadan South West. First, it will assess the impact of local costs of living and inadequate salaries on teacher retention in this area, providing a localized perspective that is currently lacking in Nigerian research. Second, the study will differentiate between the economic constraints faced by teachers in public and private ECE settings, contributing to a nuanced understanding of how these contexts affect job security, satisfaction, and retention. Finally, the research will investigate the availability of professional development resources and the financial barriers that hinder entry into the ECE profession, offering insights that could inform policy interventions aimed at improving teacher retention rates in Nigeria's ECE sector.

By addressing these areas, the study will contribute valuable data on the localized economic factors that influence teacher shortages in early childhood education, offering evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and administrators seeking to enhance teacher retention and attract new educators to this essential field.

Main Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the economic factors influencing teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) in Ibadan South West Local Government, Nigeria. The study aims to provide insights into how specific economic challenges, such as low pay, high cost of living, inadequate professional development opportunities, and job insecurity, affect teacher retention and recruitment in ECE.

Specific Purposes of the Study

To assess the impact of low salaries and local costs of living on ECE teacher retention in Ibadan South West.

To analyze the economic constraints faced by teachers in public versus private ECE settings in Ibadan South West and how these factors contribute to teacher shortages.

To examine the influence of inadequate professional development and financial support on teacher retention in ECE.

To investigate the financial barriers to entering the ECE profession and how these affect the availability of qualified teachers in Ibadan South West.

To explore the extent to which job insecurity influences teacher retention among private ECE teachers in Ibadan South West.

Research Questions

How do low salaries and the local cost of living affect teacher retention in early childhood education in Ibadan South West?

What are the differences in economic constraints faced by public and private ECE teachers in Ibadan South West, and how do these constraints contribute to teacher shortages?

How do inadequate professional development opportunities and lack of financial support influence teacher retention in ECE in Ibadan South West?

What financial barriers exist for individuals seeking to enter the ECE teaching profession in Ibadan South West, and how do these barriers affect the supply of qualified teachers?

How does job insecurity influence the retention of private ECE teachers in Ibadan South West?

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to examine the economic factors influencing teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) in Ibadan South West Local Government, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was chosen to allow for the collection of data on participants' experiences, attitudes, and perceptions, which helped in understanding the economic challenges impacting teacher retention and recruitment in ECE.

Population and Sample

The study population consisted of all early childhood education teachers in both public and private schools in Ibadan South West Local Government. A sample of approximately 200 teachers (100 from public and 100 from private schools) was selected using a stratified random sampling method. This approach ensured representation from both public and private ECE teachers, allowing for a comparative analysis of economic constraints across these groups.

Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to measure the key variables related to each research question. The questionnaire included both closed and open-ended questions to capture quantitative data. Key sections of the questionnaire covered:

Teacher Demographics: Included age, gender, years of experience, qualification level, and current employment status.

Economic Factors: Questions related to salary levels, cost of living in Ibadan South West, and perceived job security.

Professional Development Opportunities: Questions about access to training, support for further education, and any financial support for professional development.

Financial Barriers to Entry: Items on the costs of training, certification, and other financial barriers affecting entry into the ECE field.

Teacher Retention: Questions addressing job satisfaction, intention to stay or leave the profession, and factors contributing to job retention or turnover.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in early childhood education and educational research to confirm that it effectively measured the constructs of interest. A pilot study was conducted with a small subset of teachers (approximately 20) to refine the questionnaire items based on feedback. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument, with an acceptable threshold set at 0.7.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics:

Descriptive Statistics: Mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages were calculated to provide an overview of teachers' economic conditions, job security, and access to resources.

Comparative Analysis: Independent sample t-tests or ANOVA were used to compare responses from public and private school teachers, especially concerning differences in economic constraints and job security.

Correlation Analysis: Pearson correlation was conducted to assess relationships between economic factors (e.g., salary, cost of living) and teacher retention variables.

Results

Table 1

Effect of Low Salaries and Cost of Living on Teacher Retention in ECE (N = 200)

variable	Mean(M)	SD	Retention intension correlation (r)	P
Salary level (Naira/ Month	40,000	8,500	.52	.001
Local Cost of living	3.8	0.7	-.48	.001

Note: $P < .01$

Interpretation: The results indicate that salary level positively correlates with teacher retention intention ($r = .52, p < .01$), suggesting that higher salaries are associated with greater teacher retention. Conversely, a high cost of living is negatively correlated with retention intention ($r = -.48, p < .01$), implying that economic pressure from living costs may drive teachers to seek other employment opportunities. These findings highlight the significance of salary improvements for retention in ECE.

Table 2

Economic Constraints Faced by Public vs. Private ECE Teachers in Ibadan South West (N = 200)

Economic Factor	Public Teachers (M)	SD	Private Teachers (M)	SD	T	P
Salary Level (Naira/month)	45,000	6,000	35,000	8,000	4.12	.001
Job Security (1-5 Scale)	3.4	0.9	2.0	1.1	5.24	.001
Cost of Living Impact (1-5 Scale)	4.0	0.8	3.6	0.9	2.48	.01
Access to Professional Development	2.7	0.8	1.9	0.9	4.38	.001

Note: $p < .01, p < .05$.

Interpretation: Public ECE teachers reported significantly higher salaries and job security levels compared to private teachers ($p < .01$ for both). Furthermore, private teachers experienced a higher impact of cost-of-living pressures ($M = 4.0$) and less access to professional development ($M = 1.9$). These constraints may make it harder for private schools to retain teachers, contributing to teacher shortages in private ECE settings.

Table 3

Influence of Professional Development and Financial Support on Teacher Retention (N = 200)

Variable	Mean (M)	SD	Retention	P
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			intention Correlation (r)	
Access to Professional Development	2.3	0.9	.44	.001
Financial Support for Development	2.1	1.0	.42	.001

Note: $p < .01$.

Interpretation: The results show a moderate positive correlation between access to professional development and retention intention ($r = .44, p < .01$), as well as between financial support and retention ($r = .42, p < .01$). Teachers with greater access to training and financial support tend to stay longer in the profession, highlighting the need for enhanced development opportunities to improve teacher retention in ECE.

Table 4

Financial Barriers to Entering the ECE Teaching Profession and Teacher Supply (N = 200)

Barrier	Mean Rating (1-5 Scale)	SD	Impact on Supply Correlation (r)	p
Training Costs	4.1	0.6	-.51	.001
Certification Fees	3.8	0.7	-.45	.001
Lack of Financial Aid	4.3	0.5	-.47	.001

Note: $p < .01$.

Interpretation: High training costs, certification fees, and limited financial aid negatively correlate with the supply of qualified teachers (all $p < .01$). These financial barriers discourage entry into the ECE teaching profession, reducing the overall pool of available teachers in Ibadan South West. Reducing these barriers could help alleviate teacher shortages.

Table 5

Influence of Job Insecurity on Retention of Private ECE Teachers (N = 100)

Variable	Mean (M)	SD	Retention Intention Correlation (r)	P
Job Insecurity	2.0	1.1	-.53	.001

Note: $p < .01$.

Interpretation: Job insecurity showed a strong negative correlation with retention

intention among private ECE teachers ($r = -.53, p < .01$), indicating that teachers with low job security are less likely to remain in the profession. This suggests that providing greater job stability could be a key factor in retaining private ECE teachers in Ibadan South West.

Discussion of Findings

1. Effect of Low Salaries and Cost of Living on Teacher Retention

The study found that low salaries and high local costs of living significantly impact teacher retention in early childhood education (ECE). Higher salaries correlated positively with retention, while increased cost of living pressures had a negative effect. This finding is consistent with Flores and Craig (2023), who identified low pay as a major reason for ECE teacher shortages in Nigeria, where salaries often fail to meet even basic personal needs. Similarly, Ingersoll, May, and Collins (2019) highlighted that inadequate salaries contribute to teacher shortages in the United States, suggesting that economic strains are a universal factor in retaining ECE educators.

This study aligns with Edwards and Cheok (2018), who noted that urban living costs further compound retention difficulties, especially in areas where teachers lack financial support. In Ibadan South West, the high cost of living paired with low salaries limits teachers' ability to meet financial obligations, thus reinforcing the need for policy interventions to increase teacher compensation as a retention strategy.

2. Differences in Economic Constraints for Public and Private ECE Teachers

Public and private ECE teachers face different economic constraints, with private school teachers reporting lower salaries, less job security, and reduced access to professional development. This finding supports Mlangeni et al. (2015), who found that job insecurity is a significant issue for teachers, particularly in private institutions, where temporary contracts and lower salaries are common. McGrath et al. (2020) also noted that job instability impacts teacher retention, especially for male teachers, suggesting that employment uncertainty has widespread implications on workforce stability.

In Ibadan South West, public school teachers benefit from relatively better pay and stability, making private ECE teachers more susceptible to attrition. These results affirm Cobbold (2015), who emphasized the importance of funding for improving job security and teacher retention. This gap in support between public and private institutions in Ibadan suggests that private ECE settings may struggle more significantly with teacher shortages, and addressing these constraints through better job security and development opportunities could mitigate this disparity.

3. Impact of Professional Development and Financial Support on Teacher Retention

The study also found that access to professional development and financial support is positively associated with teacher retention, as teachers with more resources for development and training are more likely to stay in the profession. This aligns with Piphon (1998), who emphasized the role of professional training in maintaining a

qualified teaching workforce. Without adequate funding for development, teacher shortages are likely to persist, as seen in both Nigeria and other contexts where training resources are limited.

This finding also agrees with Lamboy (2023), who argued that insufficient funding for in-service training limits the growth of teachers and, by extension, the quality of early childhood education. In this study, the correlation between development opportunities and retention intention highlights that improving professional development resources could be a critical step toward addressing teacher shortages in ECE.

4. Financial Barriers to Entering the ECE Teaching Profession

The results demonstrated that financial barriers, such as high training costs and lack of financial aid, significantly deter individuals from entering the ECE teaching profession in Ibadan South West, thereby reducing the supply of qualified teachers. This finding supports Reinsfield and Lee (2021) and Glackin and Adams (2016), who argued that high entry costs deter prospective teachers from low-income backgrounds, exacerbating teacher shortages. Shein (2019) similarly emphasized that high certification fees discourage individuals from pursuing teaching, reducing the number of qualified teachers available for ECE roles.

In Nigeria, where financial support for training is limited, the high costs associated with entering the profession serve as a substantial barrier, contributing to the shortage of ECE teachers. These findings underline the necessity of financial incentives and subsidies to encourage more individuals to pursue ECE teaching.

5. Influence of Job Insecurity on Retention of Private ECE Teachers

The study found that job insecurity negatively impacts retention intention among private ECE teachers. Teachers who felt uncertain about their employment were significantly less likely to remain in the profession. This finding is consistent with Mlangeni et al. (2015), who reported that job instability drives away potential and existing teachers in Malawi, and McGrath et al. (2020), who noted similar effects worldwide, especially in regions with unstable employment conditions. These results imply that addressing job security issues, especially in private ECE settings in Ibadan South West, could be critical in improving retention rates.

Given that private institutions are more likely to employ teachers on temporary contracts with limited job security, these findings highlight the need for policies that offer greater stability to teachers. Providing secure contracts and long-term benefits could be an effective approach for private institutions to retain qualified teachers, ultimately supporting continuity in early childhood education.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

This study examined the economic factors influencing teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) within Ibadan South West Local Government. The study

specifically analyzed factors such as low salaries, local cost of living, differences in economic constraints between public and private ECE teachers, inadequate professional development opportunities, financial barriers to entry, and job insecurity. Utilizing the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model as a theoretical framework, the research highlighted how both economic demands and limited resources impact teacher retention and recruitment in ECE. The findings suggest that low salaries, high local living costs, lack of professional development, job insecurity, and financial barriers to entering the teaching profession significantly affect teacher retention and recruitment in early childhood education.

The study's findings align with international and national research on ECE teacher shortages, reinforcing the role of economic factors as substantial barriers to retention. Each research question provided insight into specific economic constraints and their implications, offering a comprehensive understanding of how these factors contribute to the shortage of qualified teachers in ECE in Ibadan South West.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the pressing need to address economic constraints affecting teacher retention in early childhood education in Ibadan South West Local Government. Addressing low salaries, job insecurity, and financial barriers is critical to creating a stable, well-resourced, and dedicated ECE workforce. By implementing the recommended strategies and fostering economic and professional support, educational stakeholders in Ibadan and similar contexts can make significant strides toward ensuring quality education for young children and strengthening the overall foundation of the education sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations should be considered to address the economic factors contributing to teacher shortages in early childhood education (ECE) in Ibadan South West:

Policymakers should advocate for increased salaries and comprehensive benefits for early childhood educators. This adjustment would help teachers meet their basic needs and enhance the attractiveness of the teaching profession, encouraging retention and recruitment.

Schools and educational authorities should develop financial incentive programs, such as bonuses for experienced teachers and those pursuing professional development. These incentives can motivate teachers to remain in the profession and seek further education.

Education stakeholders should prioritize the establishment of accessible and affordable professional development programs. Regular training sessions, workshops, and online courses should be made available to equip teachers with the skills necessary to excel in their roles.

Government and educational institutions should work to create more permanent positions within early childhood education. Ensuring job security can significantly improve teacher morale and retention rates.

Local governments and educational authorities should consider implementing housing subsidies or assistance programs for teachers, especially in urban areas where the cost of living is high. Such support can alleviate financial pressures and contribute to teacher retention.

Governments should allocate more resources to the education sector, particularly early childhood education. Increased funding would facilitate the development of training programs, improve working conditions, and ultimately enhance the quality of education provided.

Awareness campaigns should be initiated to promote early childhood education as a viable and rewarding career choice. These campaigns should highlight the importance of ECE and the positive impact teachers can have on children's development.

Educational institutions should establish mentorship programs that pair experienced teachers with new educators. Such initiatives can provide valuable support, reduce feelings of isolation, and enhance job satisfaction among novice teachers.

Schools should encourage community engagement in the ECE sector. By fostering partnerships with local organizations and businesses, schools can create a supportive network that benefits both teachers and students.

Educational authorities should conduct regular assessments of the working conditions and needs of ECE teachers. Gathering feedback from educators can help identify specific challenges and inform policy decisions aimed at improving the profession.

Implications for Policy and Practice

This study offers critical insights for educational policymakers, administrators, and institutions in Ibadan South West and similar regions:

Policy: By emphasizing the significance of economic factors, this study advocates for policies that align teacher salaries with the local cost of living and enhance job security, particularly in private ECE institutions. These policy adjustments are essential for addressing the economic barriers that lead to teacher attrition.

Practice: For ECE centers, fostering a supportive environment that prioritizes professional development and stability can be instrumental in retaining teachers. By implementing such practices, these institutions can create a more sustainable and attractive teaching environment for ECE educators.

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